

Informing Ridge to Reef fluxes of fine sediment in Queensland, Australia, a summary of project results from an Advance Queensland Industry Research Fellowship

Daniel Livsey⁺

⁺ Advance Queensland Industry Research Fellow, Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2028-6128

Citation: Livsey, D. N. (2023). Informing Ridge to Reef fluxes of fine sediment in Queensland, Australia. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258263>

Abstract

This report summarises results from an Advance Queensland Industry Research Fellowship focused on advancing monitoring and understanding of fine sediment delivery from rivers to the Great Barrier Reef (GBR) in Queensland, Australia. The primary goals of the fellowship were to 1) develop methods to measure the quantity (“load”) and particle size of suspended riverine sediment and 2) advance understanding of fine sediment delivery from rivers to the Great Barrier Reef in Queensland, Australia. Measuring riverine suspended-sediment loads by particle size is important because smaller sediment particles are more likely to be transported offshore and impair GBR water quality when compared to larger particles that settle more quickly and more readily deposit on the landscape or in the near-shore (Livsey et al., 2022). Key fellowship outcomes include: 1) development of new sensor technology to measure the load and particle size of fine sediment most likely to cause sediment-related water quality impairments in the GBR (Livsey et al., 2023a) and 2) improved understanding of processes affecting fine sediment delivery from upland catchments (“Ridge”) and across to the GBR (“Reef”) (Livsey et al., 2022, 2023b). Field-based measurements indicate that the fraction of fine sediment (i.e., sediment < 20 µm) most likely to cause sediment-related water quality impairments in the GBR varies between rivers surveyed from < 6% to 50% (Livsey et al., 2022); while, coupled hydrodynamic-sediment transport models indicate that the percent of catchment sediment transported offshore to the GBR depends largely on deposition or erosion in the coastal floodplain where river flow is affected by tides (Livsey 2023b). Fellowship results are significant for Queensland because monitoring and comparison of the < 20 µm sediment load between catchments can aid in the implementation of land management practices that aim to enhance GBR resiliency to climate change through reductions in sediment-related water quality impairments (Livsey et al., 2022).

Project Summary

Along the Great Barrier Reef (GBR), riverine sediment <20 µm has been shown to readily disperse across the GBR lagoon and impair the ecosystem health of coral reefs and seagrass meadows through: (a) impacts on water clarity that affect photosynthesis, (b) introduction of disease vectors, (c) direct impairments to fish gill function, and (d) impacts on seagrass biogeochemistry (Livsey et al., 2022 and references therein). When compared to larger particles, sediment <20 µm is more readily dispersed from rivers and across to the GBR because larger particles settle more quickly and more readily deposit on the landscape or in the near shore (Livsey et al., 2022). Given the societal, economic, and ecologic importance of the GBR to Queensland, an Advance Queensland Industry Research Fellowship was funded by the Queensland Department of Tourism, Innovation and Sport to develop methods to enable industry partners to measure the percent of catchment load that is less than 20 µm (Livsey et al., 2023a). This work was needed because current monitoring programs measure sediment loads without delineation of particle size. Fellowship results are significant for Queensland because monitoring and comparison of the < 20 µm sediment load between catchments can aid in the implementation of land management practices that aim to enhance GBR resiliency through reductions in sediment-related water quality impairments (Livsey et al., 2022a). Below, key results relevant to processes affecting the routing of fine sediment from Queensland catchment

and across to the GBR are summarized. Detailed reports on methods, results, and implications are provided in Livsey et al (2022, 2023a,b) and Livsey (in review).

Key result 1: The amount of fine sediment readily dispersed from “Ridge” to “Reef” varies across rivers owing to the aggregation and disaggregation of clay and silt.

In-situ particle size measurements indicate that more than 80% of suspended riverine sediment in Queensland catchments is comprised of silt and clay and that changes in the amount of fine sediment $< 20 \mu\text{m}$ is determined primarily by the aggregation and disaggregation of silt and clay particles, a process known as “flocculation” (Figure 1; Livsey et al., 2022). The prevalence of flocculation across Queensland catchments was not previously reported due to a lack of in-situ particle size measurements. Prior to this fellowship, riverine sediment particle size was measured in the laboratory following disaggregation of sediment collected in water samples (Figure 1). Due to flocculation, in-situ particle size measurements are critical for quantifying particle size of riverine sediment because laboratory-measured particle size may not reflect in-stream particle size (Figure 1). The process of flocculation is especially important to note when understanding the routing of fine sediment from “Ridge” to “Reef” because, “the settling velocity of suspended sediment, along with prevailing currents, controls sediment dispersal distance” and “[Current] sediment transport models, utilized to track progress toward water quality targets, assume fine sediment is transported as individual, 1–10 μm , slow-settling (0.01–0.1 mm/s) particles... [thus], current models may incorrectly estimate sediment dispersal if suspended sediment is flocculated” (Livsey et al., 2022).

Figure 1. (a) Boxplot of median particle size by sample for all in-situ and dispersed measurements collected in nine north Queensland, Australia rivers from February to April 2021. Boxes extend to interquartile range, the horizontal line in each box is the median value. Upper and lower whiskers extend to the 0.975 and 0.025 quantiles, respectively. Circles indicate the minimum and maximum values. Number of samples (n) indicated above each box. Inset: ratio of median particle size by volume (D_{50v}) for all paired in-situ and dispersed particle size measurements compared to sample elevation normalized by total depth. (b) Comparison of the mean particle size distributions by volume across all in-situ and dispersed measurements with the probability distribution function (PDF), and cumulative distribution function (CDF) normalized to one. Reproduced from Livsey et al (2022).

Key result 2: New sensor technology needed to monitor suspended-sediment load under changes in particle size and density was developed.

In-situ particle size measurements indicate that riverine sediment constantly changes particle size and density as silt and clay aggregates (“flocs”) aggregate or disaggregate depending on the concentration of suspended-sediment, current velocity, and salinity (Livsey et al., 2022). Changes in particle size and density presented a great challenge as fellowship methods originally aimed to use acoustic backscatter sensors to monitor sediment load and current methods cannot continuously monitor changes in sediment concentration and particle size under changes in particle density (Livsey et al., 2023a). To overcome this challenge, new sensor technology was developed by combining optical and acoustic backscattering sensors (Livsey et al., 2023a). By combining optical and acoustic backscattering sensors, the concentration and particle size of suspended sediment can be simultaneously measured even under changes in floc density (Figure 2; Livsey et al., 2023a).

Combining optical and acoustic backscattering sensors to measure sediment loads by particle size should enhance monitoring and reduce cost. Prior to publication of Livsey et al (2023a) monitoring of sediment loads by particle size required the use of laser-based sensors costing nearly \$100,000 AUD for each sensor. In Livsey et al (2023a), a lower-cost sensor combining optical and acoustic sensors may be purchased for a nominal cost of \$25,000 AUD. Cost to monitoring programs should be further minimized because the optical and acoustic sensors used in Livsey et al (2023a) are utilized widely across existing monitoring programs in Queensland and internationally.

With adoption of methods in Livsey et al (2023a) additional measurements of fine sediment particle size would become more widely available and would enable workers to more accurately measure the effectiveness of land management practices that aim to protect the GBR from sediment-related water quality impairments. To facilitate adoption of fellowship methods in Queensland and at the national level a guideline was prepared under Australia’s National Industry Guidelines for hydrometric monitoring (Livsey, in review).

Figure 2. Comparison of predicted quantities to observed values across all datasets using combined measurements of optical and acoustic backscatter. Reproduced from Livsey et al (2023a).

Key result 3: The amount of catchment sediment transported from “Ridge” to “Reef” depends largely on deposition or erosion in the coastal floodplain where river flow is affected by tides.

To further explore the implications of fine sediment flocculation on “Ridge” to “Reef” fluxes, coupled hydrodynamic-sediment transport models were implemented for the Normanby River flood plain (Livsey et al., 2023b), the Johnstone Estuary (Livsey et al., 2023b), and the Fitzroy Estuary (Xio et al., 2023). Sediment transport models were implemented assuming non-flocculated and flocculated sediment and for “low-flow” and “high-flow” years (Figure 3). The key result from this work indicated that the amount of catchment sediment delivered to the GBR varied between catchments and with time. The amount of catchment sediment delivered to the GBR varies as a function of particle size, river flow magnitude, and the length of the river affected by tides (Livsey et al., 2023b). During low-flow years, up-to 100% of catchment sediment may be trapped in the tidally influenced portion of Queensland rivers; however, during higher-flow years 100% of catchment sediment can be delivered to the GBR with additional riverine sediment delivered to the GBR from erosion in the tidally influenced portion of Queensland rivers. The influence of trapping and erosion in the tidally influenced portion rivers increases with catchment area and

the length of the river affected by tides. That is, for the largest rivers additional trapping of catchment sediment is expected compared to smaller rivers with shorter tidally affected river reaches. Smaller particles tended to be trapped less, but because of flocculation, enhanced by saline water in the tidal reaches, more than 80% of catchment sediment is expected to be affected by potential trapping in the tidal reaches of Queensland catchments (Livsey et al., 2022).

These results have important implications for monitoring and modelling fluxes of fine sediment and absorbed constituents along the Ridge to Reef continuum. Along the Ridge to Reef continuum, the tidal domain is expected to have the largest impact on the storage of fine sediment and absorbed constituents. Current monitoring and modelling used to track GBR water quality targets often omit processes in the tidal reaches of Queensland rivers (Livsey et al., 2023b). Since deposition and erosion in tidal reaches varies across catchments and years, comparing water quality impairments from catchment inputs measured upstream of the coast on the GBR lagoon and Reef could be biased by omission of processes in this domain (Livsey et al., 2023b).

Figure 3. Modelled suspended-sediment concentration during peak sediment discharge in 2011 for the Johnstone River estuary assuming $< 20 \mu\text{m}$ sediment (a) and $100 \mu\text{m}$ sediment (b). Trapping efficiency (i.e., the proportion of catchment sediment deposited in the coastal floodplain and not transported to the GBR lagoon) varies with particle size and between high-flow “Wet year” and low-flow “Dry year” years. Modified from Livsey et al (2023b).

Future Recommendations

Detailed recommendations for ongoing monitoring and modelling of fine sediment dispersal from river to the Great Barrier Reef are provided in Livsey et al (2022, 2023a, b). Below key recommendations are summarised.

- To compare risk of sediment-related impairments more robustly on Great Barrier Reef water quality across catchments, monitoring efforts would benefit from comparing the < 20 µm load instead of total load measurements without delineation of particle size (Livsey et al., 2022). Monitoring the < 20 µm load requires routine estimates of the < 20 µm fraction since changes in floc size result in constantly changing particle size. Combined optical and acoustic backscatter sensor measurements can be used to continuously estimate the < 20 µm load (Livsey et al., 2023a).
- To more accurately compare catchment loads delivered from catchments to the Great Barrier Reef lagoon, additional monitoring stations are needed at the terminus of rivers (i.e., coast). For some catchments, current modelling programs use sediment core data to estimate a constant trapping estimate in the tidal reaches of Queensland rivers. Application of trapping estimates from sediment cores is of concern because river discharge, geomorphology, and in-stream particle size vary most within the tidal domain and between catchments and years (Livsey et al., 2023b).
- Models linking non-tidal catchment models to marine models are likely needed to better compare risk of water quality impairments between catchments and across years since sediment loads from non-tidal monitoring or modelling stations may not equal loads observed at the coast where rivers discharge to the Great Barrier Reef lagoon (Livsey et al., 2023b)

Acknowledgements

Funding for this research was provided by an Advance Queensland Industry Research Fellowship, Queensland University of Technology, and Queensland Department of Environment and Science.

References

Livsey, D. N., Crosswell, J. R., Turner, R. D. R., Steven, A. D. L., & Grace, P. R. (2022). Flocculation of Riverine Sediment Draining to the Great Barrier Reef, Implications for Monitoring and Modeling of Sediment Dispersal Across Continental Shelves. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 127(7), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JC017988>.

Livsey, D. N., Turner, R. D. R., & Grace, P. R. (2023a). Combining Optical and Acoustic Backscatter Measurements for Monitoring of Fine Suspended-Sediment Concentration Under Changes in Particle Size and Density. *Water Resources Research*, 59(8), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022WR033982>.

Livsey, D.N., Turner, R., Grace P., (2023b). Informing Ridge to Reef fluxes of fine sediment and absorbed constituents. Invited oral presentation, Ecosciences Precinct Dutton Park, QLD Australia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796581>

Livsey, D.N. (in review). National Industry Guidelines for hydrometric monitoring—Part 12: Application of acoustic Doppler velocity meters to measure suspended-sediment load. Bureau of Meteorology. Melbourne, Australia

Xiao, Z., Carlin, G., Steven, A. D., Livsey, D. N., Song, D., & Crosswell, J. R. (2023). A measurement-to-modelling approach to understand catchment-to-reef processes: sediment transport in a highly turbid estuary. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1215161>